

An in vitro Investigation of the Accuracy Levels of Different Electronic Apex Locators

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ABSTRACT

This in vitro study aimed to assess the accuracy of different electronic apex locator (EAL) devices in determining the working length (WL) of root canals at varying battery charge levels (full, half, and low). The objective was to evaluate whether battery charge influences WL measurement precision, as accurate determination is essential for the success of endodontic treatment. Twenty fully developed human mandibular premolars were selected and examined under a dental surgical microscope (OMS 2000, Zumax, China) to exclude teeth with fractures, resorption, or root curvature. Access cavities were prepared using tungsten carbide burs, and #10 K-files were inserted until the apical foramen was visible. The actual WL was measured using a digital caliper (Mitutoyo Corp., Tokyo, Japan) with a precision of ± 0.01 mm. To standardize testing conditions, teeth and EAL clips were embedded in custom-made alginate models. Three EAL devices—Dte Dpex III Gold, Woodpex-3 Gold Plus, and Dte Dpex V—were tested at three battery charge levels. Each condition was evaluated in triplicate to ensure reliability. The EAL measurements were compared with actual WL values, and statistical analysis was performed using two-way repeated measures ANOVA (Greenhouse-Geisser correction) in IBM SPSS 25 to examine the impact of charge level and device type on measurement accuracy. The results showed no statistically significant differences in WL measurements among different battery charge levels ($p > 0.05$). All three EAL devices provided consistent and reliable readings, closely aligning with the actual WL. Descriptive statistics confirmed that the mean measurements for each device and charge condition were within an acceptable range of the true WL, demonstrating the robustness of these EALs regardless of battery status. The findings indicate that battery charge level does not significantly affect the accuracy of 5th-generation EAL devices in determining WL. The consistent performance of these devices, even at lower battery levels, suggests that clinicians can rely on their precision without concern for battery depletion. This reliability enhances their practicality in clinical settings, ensuring uninterrupted and accurate WL measurement during endodontic procedures.

INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of root canal treatment is to eliminate all pathogens and potential irritants from the root canal system (1). Therefore, accurate determination of the working length (WL) is critical to ensure that all endodontic instruments, irrigation solutions, medicaments, and root canal filling materials remain confined within the root canal system during endodontic treatment (2). Studies have shown that debris can extrude

through the apical foramen even when all phases of root canal treatment are confined within the root canal cavity (3).

Accurate WL determination is a crucial factor for the success of endodontic treatment (4). Errors such as short measurements or measurements beyond the apical foramen can negatively affect treatment outcomes (5).

Several methods are available for determining the working length of the root canal. These methods include tactile

sensitivity, radiographic imaging and techniques, and the use of electronic apex locators (EALs) (6-9). Traditionally, the radiographic method, which involves visualizing an instrument placed inside the root canal on a radiograph, has been used for decades to determine the WL (10). However, when the apical foramen opens laterally or towards the buccal or lingual direction, determining WL using radiographs becomes challenging. The development of EALs has facilitated more accurate and predictable evaluation of WL (11).

Factors such as the diameter of the apical foramen, the type and size of the file used, the irrigation solution employed, and the electroconductivity of the pulp tissue can affect the accuracy of EALs (12, 13). Hence, careful usage of EALs is essential.

Studies on EALs have demonstrated their reliability, their ability to reduce radiation exposure during root canal treatment, and their potential to facilitate WL determination (10, 14-18). These devices are commonly utilized as auxiliary tools in many dental clinics.

Although there are numerous studies on EALs in the literature, to our knowledge, only two studies have investigated the effect of battery or charge level on the accuracy of EALs. Most EALs operate on batteries, but it is unclear whether the battery charge level affects their accuracy. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the effect of the charge level of EALs on the accuracy of working length measurements.

MÉTODOS / METHODS

Twenty human mandibular premolar teeth with completed root development were used in this study. All teeth were examined under a dental operating microscope (OMS 2000, Zumax Company, China), and teeth with cracks, resorptions, fractures, and/or curved roots, as well as teeth with open apices, were excluded from the study. Access cavities were prepared using tungsten carbide burs, and the specimens were numbered. For accurate WL measurement, #10 K-files were inserted into the canals until the tip of the file was visible at the apical foramen. The enamel-cement junction was used as a reference point to standardize access and reference points for all specimens. The distance between the file tip and stopper was measured using a digital caliper with a resolution of ± 0.01 mm (Mitutoyo Corp., Tokyo, Japan). All specimens and the EAL clips were

embedded in an alginate model specifically developed for testing the EALs.

The EALs used in this study were rechargeable Dte Dpex III Gold Apex Locator (Woodpecker, Guilin, China), Woodpex-3 Gold Plus (Woodpecker, Guilin, China), and Dte Dpex V Apex Locator (Woodpecker, Guilin, China), in accordance with the manufacturers' instructions.

Nine measurements in total were taken with three devices at three different charge levels (full, half, and low). Electronic WL measurements were first performed using fully charged Dte Dpex III Gold Apex Locator, Woodpex-3 Gold Plus, and Dte Dpex V Apex Locator. Subsequently, measurements were repeated at half charge and then at low charge levels under the same conditions, except for the differences in charge level. All measurements were recorded, and readings were considered valid if the signals from the EALs remained stable for 5 seconds.

The difference between measurements was calculated for each tooth by subtracting the real WL from the electronic WL. Positive values indicated measurements beyond the apical constriction, negative values indicated measurements short of the apical constriction, and values of 0.0 were considered coinciding measurements.

Descriptive statistics (count, percentage, mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum) were calculated for the data. Assumptions of normal distribution were tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test, homogeneity of variance was assessed using Levene's test, and sphericity was evaluated with Mauchly's W test. Two-way repeated measures ANOVA (Greenhouse-Geisser statistic) was used to evaluate the interaction effects between independent and dependent groups that met the assumption of normality. Analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS 25 software.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the maximum and minimum measured values obtained from measurements made with various EABs at different battery charge levels.

Table 1. Minimum and maximum values of measurements according to devices and charging status.

	Full	Half	Low
	Min.-Max.	Min.-Max.	Min.-Max.
At the apex	17.2-23.8	17.2-23.8	17.2-23.8
Dte Dpex V Apex Locator	17.6-24.4	17.5-23.7	18.9-23.6
Dte Dpex III Gold Apex Locator	17.8-23.7	2.2-24.4	18.1-24.2
Woodpex-3 Gold Plus	17.8-23.7	17.6-24.2	18.3-24

Min: Minimum, Max: Maximum.

Table 2. Distribution and comparison of measurements according to devices and charging status.

	Full	Half	Low	
	Mean± SD (Med.)	Mean± SD (Med.)	Mean± SD (Med.)	
At the apex	20.97±1.40(20.99)	20.97±1.40(20.99)	20.97±1.40(20.99)	
Dte Dpex V Apex Locator	20.87±1.55(20.87)	20.87±1.50(21.05)	21.07±1.38(21.25)	
Dte Dpex III Gold Apex Locator	20.67±1.34(20.67)	20.21±4.31(20.8)	20.85±1.51(20.85)	
Woodpex-3 Gold Plus	20.71±1.34(20.76)	21.13±1.37(21.25)	21.47±1.41(21.49)	
	Type 3 Squares Total of	Squares Average of	F	p
Charge	4,995	1,226	4,076	1,813
Charge * Device	6,830	3,677	1,858	0.826

SD: Standard deviation, Med: Median.

Table 2 shows that there is no significant difference between the measurements made at all charge levels. Also, no significant difference was found in the measurements made at all charge levels in all three devices. When the real DB (at the apex) and electronic DB values were compared, it was seen that consistent readings were made in different devices and at different charge levels.

The distribution of measurements according to devices and charging status is given in the table and the comparison is made by Two-Way ANOVA test. As a result of the analysis, no statistically significant differences were obtained according to charging status and devices and it was determined that the charging status*device interaction effect was insignificant ($p>0.05$).

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show that similar results were obtained with the real DC in measurements made with different devices at three charge levels.

Figure 1. Histogram graph of the distribution of measurements according to devices and charging status

Figure 2. Box plot of the distribution of measurements according to devices and charging status.

DISCUSSION

Previous studies have shown that EALs are more reliable for WL determination compared to radiographic methods (19, 20). Additionally, the reduction of radiation exposure through the use of EALs may influence clinicians to prefer EALs over radiographs for WL determination (21). Hence, this study compared three EALs (Dte Dpex III Gold Apex Locator, Woodpex-3 Gold Plus) without the use of radiographic or other methods.

In this study, mandibular premolars with straight, single canals were selected to eliminate anatomical challenges during WL determination. Furthermore, an alginate model was used to ensure standardization in measurements, as done in previous studies (4, 12, 20, 22).

Many studies have compared various EALs to evaluate their superiority (23-26). However, no studies using the devices in this study were found in the literature.

There are only two studies evaluating whether different charge levels affect the accuracy of EALs, and their results showed that charge levels influenced measurement accuracy (4, 5). All devices used in this study are fifth-generation EALs. The consistent measurements observed at different charge levels may be attributed to the quality and features of these fifth-generation devices, which measure capacitance and resistance separately, ensuring accurate readings regardless of battery charge levels. Additionally, low battery levels do not produce erroneous results.

Within the limitations of this in vitro study, it was concluded that different devices provide acceptable results at varying charge levels. However, low charge levels may lead to measurement deviations..

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